

Study Protocol for A Randomized Controlled Trial Evaluating the Impact of Menstrual Phase–Based Exercise Compared to Regular Exercise on Reproductive Hormones, Pain Profiles, And Quality of Life in Eumenorrheic Women with Primary Dysmenorrhea

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ABSTRACT

Background: Primary dysmenorrhea (PD) significantly impairs quality of life in young women. While exercise is a known intervention, the specific impact of tailoring exercise intensity to menstrual cycle phases (phase-based) versus standard non-synchronized exercise remains unexplored. **Methods:** This single-blind, parallel-group Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) will be conducted over two years in Sangli, India. Eumenorrheic women (18–25 years) with PD will be randomized into two groups: (A) Menstrual Phase-Based Exercise (n=34) and (B) Regular Standard Exercise (n=34). Interventions last 12 weeks. **Outcomes:** The primary outcome is the change in serum Estradiol (E2) and Progesterone (P4) levels measured in the early follicular phase. Secondary outcomes include pain characteristics (WaLLIDE score) and Quality of Life (PERIOD-QOL). **Hypothesis:** Menstrual phase-based exercise will yield superior or equivalent improvements in hormonal regulation and pain reduction compared to regular exercise. **Discussion:** This study seeks to validate a "cycle-synced" rehabilitation framework, potentially offering a personalized non-pharmacological alternative to analgesics.

Keywords: Primary Dysmenorrhea, Menstrual Cycle, Therapeutic Exercise, Phase-Based Training, Reproductive Hormones, Quality of Life.

INTRODUCTION

Primary dysmenorrhea (PD) is defined as painful menstrual cramps in the lower abdomen occurring shortly before or during menstruation without identifiable pelvic pathology. It affects up to 90% of adolescent and reproductive-age women, significantly impairing their quality of life (QOL) and causing frequent absenteeism from school or work. The key pathophysiological mechanism involves excessive secretion of uterine prostaglandins, mainly PGF_{2α} and PGE₂, leading to increased uterine contractions, ischemia, and sensitization of pain fibers. The cyclic decline of progesterone after ovulation triggers increased prostaglandin production from the endometrium, which correlates with symptom

severity. PD often coexists with premenstrual syndrome (PMS), which involves shared neuroendocrine and inflammatory pathways affecting overall well-being. (1-4) Existing trials show exercise reduces dysmenorrhea pain intensity by 1.8-2.6 cm on the VAS scale, with strength training and protocols of ≥8 weeks, >3 sessions weekly, and >90 minutes total proving most effective. However, these studies use non-synchronized regimens, ignoring menstrual cycle hormonal fluctuations, and lack direct comparisons of phase-based versus regular exercise on hormones, pain profiles, and quality of life. This trial is needed to test if tailoring exercises to follicular/luteal phases yields superior outcomes in eumenorrheic women with primary dysmenorrhea. (5,6)

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Current treatments predominantly involve pharmacological approaches such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and hormonal contraceptives aimed at reducing prostaglandin synthesis or suppressing ovulation. However, these treatments have limitations including side effects, contraindications, and incomplete symptom relief for many women. Non-pharmacological strategies such as physical therapies, lifestyle modifications, and exercise are gaining attention but lack robust evidence, particularly concerning how exercise timed to menstrual phases might influence hormonal regulation, pain, and quality of life. (5,7,8) Menstrual phase-based exercise, which adjusts exercise intensity in accordance with hormonal fluctuations during the menstrual cycle, has shown promise in optimizing training outcomes and symptom management. Specifically, higher intensity exercise during the follicular phase when estrogen peaks, and moderated exercise load during the luteal phase characterized by elevated progesterone, might reduce injury risk and improve recovery. Standard resistance exercises were selected as the comparator because systematic reviews identify them as the most effective non-pharmacological intervention for primary dysmenorrhea, outperforming aerobic, stretching, or yoga in pain reduction (SMD -1.89) and quality of life improvement, particularly after ≥ 8 weeks. This active control represents best current practice among exercise modalities, enabling rigorous evaluation of whether phase-based approaches provide additive benefits over this superior standard. (5,9) Benefits include significant pain reduction, improved quality of life, and hormonal balance without pharmacological risks, with low dropout rates in strength and aerobic protocols. Harms are minimal, typically limited to transient muscle soreness, with no serious adverse events reported across meta-analyses of 29+ trials; sensitivity analyses confirm effect stability. Phase-specific dosing may further minimize overexertion risks during sensitive luteal phases. (5,9,10) Yet, there is a notable scarcity of randomized controlled trials rigorously assessing the impact of menstrual phase-targeted exercise on reproductive hormones, pain characteristics, and QOL in eumenorrheic women with PD. Most studies do not precisely verify menstrual phase hormonally or connect biochemical changes to functional outcomes. Therefore, this study aims to address the research gap

by conducting a randomized controlled trial to evaluate the effects of menstrual phase-based exercise versus regular exercise on reproductive hormones, pain characteristics, and quality of life using validated tools such as the WaLLIDE and PERIOD-QOL questionnaires in healthy eumenorrheic women with primary dysmenorrhea. This approach has important clinical implications for improving non-pharmacological management of PD with personalized, symptom-synchronized exercise interventions.

Study Objectives:

Designed as a randomized controlled trial (RCT) with a duration of two years, this study aims to evaluate the comparative effects of menstrual phase-based exercise versus regular exercise on reproductive hormones, pain characteristics, and Quality of Life (QoL) in eumenorrheic women diagnosed with primary dysmenorrhea. Conducted within a semi-urban setting in the Sangli district, the primary objective is to determine the specific impact of menstrual phase-based exercise on reproductive hormone levels in contrast to regular exercise protocols. Secondary objectives include the assessment of pain characteristics—specifically location, intensity, and duration—utilizing the WaLLIDE questionnaire, as well as an evaluation of the intervention's impact on the subjects' quality of life using the PERIOD-QOL questionnaire. The study is grounded in the alternative hypothesis that menstrual phase-based exercise will demonstrate an efficacy equal to or greater than that of regular exercise regarding these parameters, contrasting with the null hypothesis which posits that the intervention will yield no significant effect on reproductive hormones, pain presentation, or quality of life in this population.

Trial Design

This study utilizes a single-blind, parallel-group randomized controlled trial (RCT) design. Due to the nature of the intervention, participants will not be blinded; however, blinding will be strictly maintained for outcome assessors and data analysts to minimize bias. The framework aims to test the alternative hypothesis that menstrual phase-based exercise yields

a superior or equivalent therapeutic effect compared to regular exercise.

Patient And Public Involvement

If patients helped review the consent form or burden of the exercise schedule

Sample:

Participants will be performed using a computer-generated randomization sequence to ensure unbiased and equal assignment to study groups (a central web-based service to prevent the researcher from predicting the next assignment.). The study protocol will be reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of BVDU School of Physiotherapy, ensuring adherence to national and international research ethics guidelines.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Females with regular menstrual cycles lasting between 21 to 35 days for the past 6 months with primary Dysmenorrhea.
2. Females aged 18–25 years.
3. No hormonal contraceptive use for at least 3 months prior to enrolment.
4. Willingness to participate, provide informed consent, and comply with study procedures.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Irregular menstrual cycles, amenorrhea, or known menstrual disorders.
2. Current or recent (within 3 months) use of hormonal contraceptives (Ethinyl estradiol with levonorgestrel, norethindrone, or drospirenone, Oral norethindrone, depot medroxyprogesterone acetate (DMPA), levonorgestrel implant/IUD) or hormonal therapy (medroxyprogesterone, norethindrone, etc).
3. Pregnancy or lactation.

4. Chronic systemic illnesses or medications affecting hormonal balance or physical activity capacity.

Allocation:

Recruit female participants aged 18–25 years with eumenorrheic menstrual cycles (21–35 days) having primary dysmenorrhea. Screen interested candidates for eligibility through questionnaire and clinical interview to ensure no contraceptive use in last 3 months, no history of pelvic pathology, and no menstrual irregularities. Obtain written informed consent from eligible participants and right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Participants will be performed using a computer-generated randomization sequence to ensure unbiased and equal assignment to study groups.

Outcomes:

participants will be Scheduled according to their menstrual cycle calendar to ensure accurate timing of assessments. Collection for baseline parameters the blood samples (venipuncture) during the early follicular phase (cycle days 3–5) to measure serum estradiol (E2) and progesterone (P4) levels. Administration of baseline WaLLIDE questionnaire to assess pain characteristics and functional impact and PERIOD-QOL questionnaire to evaluate menstrual-related quality of life.

Primary Outcomes:

Hormones

Serum Estradiol (E2) and Serum Progesterone (P4) levels. Blood samples will be collected during the early follicular phase (3–5 days after menstruation begins), reflecting hormone levels relevant to the pathophysiology of primary dysmenorrhea. These hormones influence uterine prostaglandin production and menstrual pain intensity. Reliable quantification of E2 and P4 will help assess hormonal fluctuations associated with primary dysmenorrhea severity.

Secondary Outcomes

1. Pain Characteristics

Assessed using the WaLLIDE questionnaire, which evaluates:

- Working Ability during menstruation
- Location of pain
- Pain Intensity
- Days of Pain (number of painful days per cycle)

The WaLLIDE score ranges from 0 to 12, with higher scores indicating more severe dysmenorrhea. It is validated, reliable, and sensitive to changes in menstrual pain and function.

2. Quality of Life (QOL)

Assessed using the PERIOD-QOL questionnaire, a brief 10-item self-reported tool designed specifically to measure the impact of menstruation on women's quality of life. It covers domains including physical symptoms, emotional well-being, social limitations, and work productivity. PERIOD-QOL is validated across diverse populations and sensitive to changes in menstrual-related quality of life.

Participants Timeline:

	Enrolment	Allocation	Post-randomization			Close-out
TIMEPOINT	Screening (t-1)	Baseline (0)	Weeks 1-7	Week 8 (t₁)	Weeks 9-11	Week12(t₂)
ENROLLMENT:						
Eligibility Screen	X					
Informed Consent	X					
Demographic & Medical History	X					
Randomization		X				
INTERVENTIONS:						
Group A: Menstrual Phase-Based Exercise				X		X
Group B: Regular Standard Exercise				X		X
ASSESSMENTS:						
Baseline Variables:						
BMI, Menstrual Cycle Length	X					
Outcomes:						
Serum Estradiol (E2) & Progesterone (P4)		X		X		X
Pain Characteristics (WaLLIDE)		X		X		X
Quality of Life (PERIOD-QOL)		X		X		X
Monitoring:						
Adverse Events / Adherence				X		X

Sample Size Calculation:

The design and analysis of this study utilized findings from recent menstrual cycle and exercise intervention studies to estimate the sample size for the primary endpoint of estradiol levels³. It was calculated that a sample size of 29 participants per group is required in order to have a 90% probability of demonstrating a minimum clinically important difference (MCID) of 30 pg/mL between groups (Standard Deviation: 35 pg/mL) with a significance of 5% (two-tailed test)^{4,44}. Sample size estimation was performed using the standard formula for comparison of means $n = \frac{2 \times (Z_{\alpha/2} + Z_{\beta})^2 \times \sigma^2}{\Delta^2}$. In order to account for potential attrition, a dropout rate of approximately 15% was considered; therefore, the final recruitment target was determined to be 34 participants per group⁶.

Clinical Relevance:

This study is clinically significant as it aims to validate a non-pharmacological, "cycle-synced" exercise protocol as a sustainable alternative to standard analgesic treatments, thereby reducing reliance on medication and its associated side effects. By systematically tailoring exercise intensity to the follicular and luteal phases, this research offers a novel, personalized rehabilitation framework that respects female physiological hormonal fluctuations rather than relying on generic prescriptions. Establishing this link between phase-based exercise and the regulation of serum estradiol and progesterone provides a biological basis for management, ultimately helping clinicians prescribe more effective interventions to reduce dysmenorrhea-related absenteeism and improve functional quality of life.

EQUIPMENT'S:

The following equipment and tools will be utilized to conduct the study, deliver the intervention, and assess outcomes:

1. Anthropometric & Baseline Assessment Tools

Stadiometer / Measuring Tape: To measure height (cm).

Digital Weighing Scale: To measure body weight (kg) for BMI calculation.

Menstrual Calendar / Tracking Diary: For participants to record cycle length and bleeding days to confirm inclusion criteria.

2. Intervention Equipment

Yoga Mats: For floor-based exercises (yoga, pilates, stretching) in both the intervention and control groups.

Resistance Bands: For resistance exercises during the Ovulatory and Luteal phases.

Light Dumbbells: For strength-based exercises in the Follicular and Ovulatory phases.

Stopwatch / Timer: To monitor hold times (e.g., for planks) and rest intervals between sets.

3. Outcome Measurement Tools

- Questionnaires (Printed or Digital Forms):

WaLLIDE Questionnaire: To assess pain intensity, location, and working ability.

PERIOD-QOL Questionnaire: To assess the impact of menstruation on quality of life.

- Laboratory Equipment (for Hormonal Assay):

Sterile Phlebotomy Kit: Syringes, needles, tourniquets, and cotton swabs for venous blood collection.

Serum Separator Tubes (Vacutainers): For collecting and clotting blood samples.

Centrifuge: To separate serum from blood cells.

Deep Freezer: For storage of serum samples at -20°C or lower until analysis.

Assay Kits: ELISA (Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay) or CLIA kits specifically for quantitative determination of Serum Estradiol (E2) and Progesterone (P4).

ASSESSORS:

To ensure scientific rigor and minimize bias, the study will utilize the following personnel:

- **Principal Investigator (PI)**

Responsible for overall study coordination, participant recruitment, screening against inclusion/exclusion criteria, and randomization.

Supervises the intervention sessions and monitors adherence to the home exercise program.

- **Outcome Assessor (Blinded)**

A qualified physiotherapist or research assistant, blinded to the group allocation, will administer the pre- and post-intervention questionnaires (WaLLIDE and PERIOD-QOL) to prevent observer bias.

Responsible for recording anthropometric data (Height, Weight, BMI).

- **Certified Phlebotomist**

A trained professional responsible for the safe and aseptic collection of venous blood samples during the early follicular phase (Days 3–5).

- **Laboratory Technician**

Responsible for processing blood samples (centrifugation and serum separation) and conducting the hormonal assays (Estradiol and Progesterone).

The technician will be blinded to the participants' group assignment to ensure objective biochemical analysis.

- **Exercise Supervisor**

Responsible for demonstrating the correct technique for "Phase-Based" (Group A) and "Standard" (Group

B) exercises and conducting the supervised sessions to ensure safety and protocol fidelity.

Methods: Assignment Of Interventions

Allocation

Sequence Generation:

Participants will be allocated either to Group A or Group B in a 1:1 ratio using a computer-generated randomization sequence, for example, random.org with permuted blocks of variable size 4 and 6 to ensure balance.

Allocation Concealment Mechanism:

SNOSE will be used to prevent selection bias. The SNOSE envelopes are prepared by an independent researcher not involved in participant recruitment or assessment. The envelope will only be opened after the participant has provided consent and baseline measures have been completed.

Blinding:

Participants: Cannot be blinded due to the nature of the exercise intervention.

Physiotherapists: The intervention cannot be blinded.

Outcome Assessors: The physiotherapists assessing WaLLIDE and PERIOD-QOL scores will be blinded regarding group allocation.

Laboratory technicians: Analyses of hormone assays will be blinded to participant group and time-point.

Data Analysts: Statistical analysis to be performed while blinded (groups to be labeled as X and Y).

Intervention:

Individuals diagnosed with primary dysmenorrhea will be screened for eligibility based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. The study protocol will be thoroughly explained, and written informed consent will be obtained prior to any study-related assessment. Demographic data and baseline outcome measures—including validated pain scores, quality of life (QOL) questionnaires, and reproductive hormonal assays—will be recorded for all eligible participants. Participants will be randomly assigned, using a computer-generated randomization sequence, into one of two groups:

Group A: Menstrual phase-based exercise intervention, tailored to each participant's menstrual cycle phases, administered for 12 consecutive weeks (covering 3 menstrual cycles).

Group B: Standard exercise protocol comprising resistance exercises, delivered for 12 consecutive weeks (covering 3 menstrual cycles).

The intervention in both groups will involve a combination of supervised sessions and a structured home exercise program. Adherence will be encouraged and monitored through regular telephonic follow-ups and self-maintained exercise diaries. Any adverse events will be promptly evaluated and managed by qualified healthcare professionals.

Outcome measures will be assessed at three specified time points:

- **Baseline (week 0)**
- **Interim (week 8):** An interim analysis will be performed to evaluate differences between groups with respect to pain, QOL, and hormonal outcomes. If significant benefit is observed in one group, that protocol will be adopted for all participants for the remaining 4 weeks (weeks 9–12), as decided by the research oversight committee.

- **Post-intervention (week 12):** All primary and secondary outcome measures will be reassessed.

Participants will receive appropriate support throughout, including prompt management of any health concerns and access to the study team for questions or clarifications.

Intervention Phase

Intervention Group:

Prescribe exercise regimen tailored to menstrual phases, e.g., higher intensity/volume during follicular phase when estradiol peaks and reduced intensity or active recovery during luteal/premenstrual phases.

Regarding exercise recommendations by menstrual phase:

- **Early Follicular Phase (Days 1–5):** Lower intensity activities such as light aerobic exercise,

gentle strength training, and recovery-focused workouts are suggested, considering the presence of menses and potential symptoms.

- **Late Follicular Phase (Days 6–12):** Increased energy and estrogen levels support higher intensity exercises, including strength training, high-intensity interval training (HIIT), plyometrics, and power-based workouts.
- **Ovulation (Days 13–15):** Similar to late follicular phase, this is an optimal time for power, speed, and high-intensity efforts.
- **Luteal Phase (Days 16–28):** Due to elevated progesterone and common premenstrual symptoms, recommendations lean towards moderate intensity endurance, recovery exercises, yoga,

Frequency: 3-5 sessions per week, lasting 12 weeks

Menstrual Phase	Frequency	Intensity	Duration	Exercise Type & Examples	Rationale & Reference
Menstrual Phase (Days 1–5)	Daily (5–7 days/week)	Very low intensity	20–30 minutes	Breathing exercises (diaphragmatic breathing, Nadi Shodhana), gentle yoga (Child's pose, Reclining Bound Angle), relaxation, gentle stretches	Reduces sympathetic tone, uterine ischemia, and prostaglandin synthesis to relieve pain (Patil et al., 2023)(Heidarianpour et al., 2024)(Smith et al., 2019) ⁽¹⁴⁻¹⁶⁾
Follicular Phase (Days 6–12)	4–5 days/week	Moderate intensity	30–45 minutes	Bodyweight strength exercises (squats, lunges, planks, wall push-ups), brisk walking	Rising estrogen improves muscle repair and strength; exercises improve muscle tone and circulation (AlMoney et al., 2024) (Heidarianpour et al., 2024) ^(15,17)
Ovulatory Phase (Days 13–15)	3–4 days/week	Moderate to high	30 minutes	Resistance band exercises, light dumbbells, core stability exercises (planks, bird dogs, dead bugs)	Hormonal peak enhances strength adaptations; core stability supports pelvic muscles and reduces pain (Rezvani et al., 2025)(Smith et al., 2019) ⁽¹⁶⁻¹⁸⁾

Luteal Phase (Days 16–28)	4–5 days/week	Low to moderate	30–40 minutes	Yoga (Hatha yoga, gentle twists, cat-cow, cobra pose), swimming, flexibility exercises, relaxation techniques	Progesterone phase focuses on stress reduction and symptom management to reduce PMS and dysmenorrhea symptoms (AlMoney et al., 2024)(Patil et al., 2023) ⁽¹⁴⁻¹⁵⁾
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Control Group:

matching total volume and duration with the intervention group.

Provide a standardized exercise program at consistent intensity and frequency regardless of cycle phase,

12-Week Bodyweight Resistance Exercise Protocol for Primary Dysmenorrhea

Week(s)	Frequency	Intensity	Duration	Exercises & Description	Rationale & Reference
1–4	2 days/week	Moderate	20–25 minutes	Bodyweight squats, lunges, glute bridges, wall push-ups, planks (hold 15–20 sec), bird dogs	Improves pelvic and core muscle strength; reduces menstrual pain [Xiang et al., 2025] ⁽⁵⁾
5–8	3 days/week	Moderate to high	30–35 minutes	Increase repetitions; add single-leg squats, step-ups, side planks, hip thrusts	Progressive overload improves muscular endurance and pain tolerance (Rezvani et al., 2025) ⁽⁵⁾
9–12	3 days/week	Moderate to high	40 minutes	Compound bodyweight movements: jump squats, walking lunges, dynamic plank variations, glute bridge variations	Enhances muscular support for uterus and pelvic floor, reducing uterine ischemia and pain (Fuentes-Aparicio et al., 2023) ⁽²²⁾

Additional Recommendations:

- Warm-up: 5–10 minutes of light cardio (marching on spot, arm circles).
- Cool-down: 5–10 minutes of stretching focused on lower back, hips, thighs.
- Adjust repetitions and sets according to tolerance; aim for 2–3 sets of 10–15 reps per exercise initially.

All data collected will be coded and entered into Microsoft Excel for initial cleaning and verification. The final dataset will be exported to SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 23.0 for analysis.

1. Descriptive Statistics

- **Continuous Variables:** Baseline demographic characteristics (Age, BMI, Menstrual Cycle Length) and outcome measures (Hormone levels, WALLIDE scores, PERIOD-QOL scores) will be summarized using **Mean and Standard Deviation (SD)** for normally distributed data, or

Statistical Analysis:

Data Management

Median and Interquartile Range (IQR) for non-normally distributed data.

- **Categorical Variables:** Variables such as education level or occupation will be presented as **frequencies and percentages**.

2. Normality Testing

- The **Shapiro-Wilk test** will be used to assess the normality of the distribution for all continuous variables (Estradiol, Progesterone, WaLLIDE, and PERIOD-QOL scores).
- Homogeneity of variance will be assessed using Levene's test.

3. Inferential Statistics

- **Baseline Comparability: An Independent t-test** (or Mann-Whitney U test) will be performed to compare baseline demographic and clinical characteristics between the Menstrual Phase-Based Exercise group (Group A) and the Regular Exercise group (Group B) to ensure successful randomization.

- **Intra-Group Analysis (Within-Group Changes):**

- To evaluate the effect of the intervention *within* each group (comparing Pre-test vs. Post-test values), a **Paired t-test** will be used for normally distributed data.
- If data deviates from normality, the **Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test** will be used.

- **Inter-Group Analysis (Between-Group Differences):**

- To compare the effectiveness *between* the two groups (Group A vs. Group B) at post-intervention, an **independent t-test** will be used for normally distributed data.
- If data is non-normal, the **Mann-Whitney U test** will be applied.

- **Advanced Analysis:**

- A **Repeated Measures ANOVA** (Analysis of Variance) may be conducted to analyze the interaction effect between **Time** (Pre vs. Post) and **Group** (Intervention vs. Control), enabling the determination of whether the phase-based intervention produced a significantly greater rate of improvement compared to the control.

4. Level of Significance

- For all statistical tests, a p-value of **< 0.05** will be considered statistically significant, with a 95% Confidence Interval (CI).

Ethical Considerations And Consent:

The study protocol was formally reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) of Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Medical College & Hospital, Sangli (Approval Reference Number:

BV(DU)MC&H/Sangli/IEC/Ph.D.

Dissertation/2024-25/Phy-02, dated 17/09/2025). The trial strictly adheres to national and international research ethics guidelines, including the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) guidelines, the New Drugs and Clinical Trials Rules (2019), and the Declaration of Helsinki. All participants receive detailed written and verbal information regarding the study's objective, experimental procedures, potential benefits, and risks (including blood collection and exercise-related risks), as well as rigorous data confidentiality protocols. Signed, written informed consent is obtained from each participant prior to enrollment, confirming their voluntary participation and their right to withdraw from the trial at any point without any penalty or compromise to their care. To protect participant privacy and autonomy, all personal and medical data remain strictly confidential; records are fully anonymized, securely stored, and accessed solely by authorized investigators. Any adverse events occurring during the trial will be managed immediately by qualified personnel, ensuring appropriate medical care is provided. Additionally, six-monthly progress reports and all required documentation are systematically submitted to the IEC throughout the study period.

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